

Analysis of the Impacts of Population Dynamics on Land Use and Land Cover in Nyeri Peri-Urban Area in Kenya

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Abstract

The increasing population in Nyeri County and Kenya necessitates a thoughtful, scientifically informed approach to land use and cover changes. While population is expansively elastic, land is an inelastic resource that demands sustainable utilization and planning. This study aimed to analyze land use and cover changes in Nyeri and its surroundings, emphasizing the intricate relationship between land use and population distribution. To accomplish these objectives, a dual methodology was employed. Remote sensing was utilized for land use and land cover (LULC) change analysis, employing Landsat 7 imagery from 1987, 2000, and 2010. Concurrently, GIS population mapping was employed to visually represent population distribution changes over time. Population data from the 1989, 1999, and 2009 censuses were used to examine population dynamics. The LULC analysis classified images into four categories: agricultural land, bare land, urban, and forests. The population data, converted to points at polygon centroids, underwent interpolation to map population distribution changes within the study area and across classes. Results indicated a 13% population increase between 1989 and 1999 and an 8% increase between 1999 and 2009. Urban and forest areas doubled every ten years, while cultivated land decreased by 4% initially and 15% in the second epoch. This suggested improved forest protection and heightened public awareness of their significance. Urbanization primarily impacted cultivated land, often converted into built-up areas. The findings underscore the necessity for enhanced planning to meet the evolving needs of the urban population, a significant component of the study area.

Keywords: Land use change, Population dynamics, Remote sensing, Urbanization, Sustainability

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background information

In most countries, urbanization is recognized as a crucial phenomenon for economic growth and social change as it offers increased opportunities for employment, specialization, production and goods and services (Aweke, 2013). This has made the growth of cities to accelerate physically and newer lands have had to be converted from their initial land use to new uses, whereby the new cover is majorly comprised of buildings (Li & Yan, 2020). This puts pressure on forests and necessitates a change in use to accommodate the new population.

Due to this, planners need to be aware of the two major aspects that affect the development plan of the area, that is the population growth rate as shown on previous census and the current land use especially considering the change temporal aspect of how the land has been utilized (Chilar, 2000).

1.2 Problem statement

With population increase, there is a high pressure on land. Land is an inelastic resource and hence certainly their needs to be a way of doing informed planning for the future. This will enable for poverty eradication and enable planners understand the trends and the current situation of land use and hence plan for the future.

1.3 Objectives

1. To establish how population increase has influenced land use and land cover between 1987 and 2010 in Nyeri peri-urban area, Kenya.
2. To determine how population distribution has influenced land use between 1987 and 2010 in Nyeri peri-urban area, Kenya.

1.4 Scope – Study area

The study area is in Nyeri County. The area is around Nyeri town, and covers the locations of Thigu, Kiganjo, Mukaro and Mweiga. The area is found between longitudes 37.077° and 36.834° and latitudes -0.485° and -0.306°.

Figure 1.1 Map showing the study area.

Source: Author

Nyeri town has been a major administrative town for the central Kenya since independence. However, the town has not developed to its level of prestige and historical acknowledgement. The town has poor infrastructure such as roads, poor lighting, insecurity and unemployment, poor housing and transport inefficiency. Mwangi & Orodho (2014) highlight the inadequate physical and human resources in Nyeri, underscoring the need for improved infrastructure and urban planning to address the challenges facing Nyeri. Hence, this makes the area a relevant area to study

as it has tangible issues that need to be addressed. The data is also readily available and is inexpensive to acquire since it does not involve governments classified data. The area is also endowed with resources and is in a strategic position hence the problems it faces in planning, economy and demographics are solvable (Mubea & Menz, 2014). The study area was majorly around the Nyeri town constituency. This area is considered the heart of Nyeri County and its development means much to the wider Nyeri County (Mwangi & Orodho, 2014).

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

With high population growth rate and increase in urban and built-up areas in the world, there has been enormous influence on natural land cover at different spatial extents (Aweke, 2013). Land use and land cover change is the process in which natural environments such as forests and grassland are replaced by human induced activities such as intensive agriculture and urbanization. This chapter reviews important literatures regarding land use and land cover changes as well as remote sensing and population mapping, and their application in driving forces analysis for the forces of land use change.

Land use changes globally are driving the need for food, fiber, water, and shelter, potentially undermining ecosystems' capacity to sustain food production, maintain freshwater and forest resources, regulate climate, and ameliorate infectious diseases (Foley, et al., 2005). While climate change has received enormous attention, human population growth, and the corresponding rising global demand for meat and dairy products, as well as the growing need for bioenergy from corn, sugarcane, and other sources should be equal cause for concern (Li & Yan, 2020). With 70 million new people per year, to keep up with ecosystem services and food demands, there is need to double the agricultural production of the planet in the next 30 to 40 years (Foley, et al., 2005).

Land use is the intended employment of land management strategy placed on the land cover by human agents or land managers to exploit the land cover and reflects human activities such as industrial zones, residential zones, agricultural fields, grazing, logging and mining among many others (Verburg, Groot, & Veldkamp, 2003) .

On the other hand, land cover is defined by the attributes of the earth's land surface captured in the distribution of vegetation, water, desert and ice and the immediate subsurface, including biota,

soil, topography, surface and groundwater and it also includes those structures created solely by human activities such as mine exposures and settlement (Agarwal C., 2000) .

Human activities such as deforestation, soil erosion, global warming and pollution are very harmful for the environment. This causes land use/ cover changes with the demand and supply of land in different activities (Žiga KOKAL, 2007). Change detection in land use and land cover can be performed on a temporal scale such as a decade to assess landscape change caused due to anthropogenic activities on the land (Gibson, 2000). In order to improve the economic condition of the area without further deteriorating the bio-environment, every bit of the available land has to be used in the most rational way. This requires the present and the past land use/ cover data of the area (Chaurasia, 1996) Land use/cover dynamics are widespread, accelerating and significant processes being driven by human actions but also produce changes that impact humans (Yacouba Diallo, 2009).

Prakasam, 2010, studied the land use and land cover change in the Kodaikanal region of Western Ghats in Tamil Nadu State of India to observe changes during a span of 40 years from 1969 to 2008 (Samant, 1998). Some recent studies have shown the use of remote sensing and GIS in land use change detection (Zubair, 2006).

With the invention of remote sensing and GIS techniques land use/cover mapping is a useful and detailed way to improve the selection of areas designed to agricultural, urban and/or industrial areas of a region (Chilar, 2000). Application of remotely sensed data made possible to study the changes in land cover in less time, at low cost and with better accuracy in association with GIS that provides suitable platform for data analysis, update and retrieval (Star, 1997).

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Data sources

Different remote sensing and GIS data from different sources has been used in this project.

Three medium resolution Landsat TM images of 1987, 2000 and 2010 were used to detect land cover changes in the area of study. These images were obtained from United States Geological Survey (USGS) website as standard products, i.e. geometrically and radio-metrically corrected. In order to avoid the impact of seasonal variation, images of the first quarter of the year when the study area is dry were used to reduce the effects of cloud cover. This was crucial in ensuring that cloud cover did not exceed 10%. The images also have the same spatial resolution of 30m, which

makes it convenient for comparison of changes and patterns that occurred in the time under consideration (Agarwal C., 2000).

Additionally, one VHR image covering part of Nyeri town with a resolution of 60cm was used to assist in field observation data in training the images for classification. This was acquired from Ramani Geosystems. Kenya population census data was obtained from the website of Kenya National Bureaus of Statistics, KNBS. This was acquired in shapefile format where attributed sub location polygons were used to retrieve and convert the population density data. Topographic maps and Kenya GIS data in vector formats were acquired from the Survey of Kenya headquarters.

3.2 Analysis

The analysis methodology adopted for this research was summarized in figure 2. Having identified the problem and identified the research questions, a two winged methodology was adopted. One dealt with remote sensing and the other was on population mapping which basically used GIS methods. The images used were multi-date for the years 1987, 2000 and 2010. These were standard Landsat images meaning they were geometrically corrected and were ready for further processing. The images were layerstacked using the Erdas imagine 2013 software. Image subsets were then obtained by using the vector layer outlining the area of interest.

3.3 Image classification method

Supervised classification was adopted for the research. Using the 60cm high resolution image and the topographic maps, training data was acquired and use to create signatures. The classes adopted were four i.e. bare land, build up area, agricultural and forest land. These were identified and were used across the three images. The classes for classification were chosen to be four as it was noted that they were the number necessary for analysis especially given the image resolutions for the Landsat system. It was noted that most of the bare land was actually harvested land area that could be agricultural in other images.

The urban area had almost a close reflectance to the bare land but using a high resolution aerial photograph imagery provided a good way of better separating the two near similar classes. However, the forest class was much easier to separate as it had a distinct red colour due to vegetative reflectance of the infra-red colour as red colour in the false colour composite. Once suitable training areas of distinct reflectance were identified, they were used in signature creation

for their respective classes. The signatures were then saved and used as input signature file when it came to classification.

In this study, the accuracy of the classification results for the year 2000 and 2010 are assessed using randomly sampled ground truth points, obtained from high resolution imagery. Two images were linked and using these randomly selected points, the classified image was compared against an image that had a better resolution or of a different nature. For these, the 60cm resolution image and topographic maps were used.

3.4 Production of thematic maps

The classified images were used to automatically generate the areas in hectares for the classes used. Simple differencing of NDVI images was incorporated in this study to circumvent the errors that may accrue from differencing of individual standardized spectral bands. The index is calculated using the formula:

$$\text{NDVI} = (\text{NIR} - \text{RED}) / (\text{NIR} + \text{RED})$$

Where NIR is the reflectance radiated in the near-infrared waveband (760–900 nm), and RED is the reflectance radiated in the visible red waveband (630–690 nm) of the satellite radiometer. NDVI values range between 21 and 1, with values above 0.6 indicating dense vegetation and values below 0 indicating no vegetation. Bare grounds have values of 0–0.1, grasslands have values of 0.2–0.3, while negative values correspond with water and ice surfaces.

3.5 Population mapping

The data acquired was in polygon format and had to be converted to points and their density attributes interpolated to form a raster map showing population distribution. This was done by selecting the sub locations covering the area of study and even those neighbouring the area of study. This ensured continuity of interpolation since kriging spatial analyst was to be used. These points were then saved as a new layer. Interpolation was the done and the produced raster was extracted my mask to get the study area out of the wide covering interpolation raster dataset. The ramp produced was then converted to ten classes. The classes were standard as generated by the software for the middle census (1999) but had to be adjusted to fit this for the 1989 and 2009 census.

3.6 Driving force analysis

The LULC changes and changes in population distribution and densities were analyzed by visual interpretation of the change areas within the map. These were used to draw conclusions and to explain the changes. This was made possible by use of ArcGIS software to overlay the areas and noting their dynamics with change in population. These analyses were used to find the driving forces for the changes in LULC. Processing framework.

Figure 2 methodology adopted for the study

4 CHAPTER FOUR: RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

4.1 Classification

The classified images met the 80% accuracy threshold set with the images having 81%, 87% and 83% accuracies for the years 1987, 2000 and 2010 respectively.

Figure 3 Land cover classified image for the years 1987, 2000 and 2010

The classified images displayed increase in urban areas and forest area while there was inconclusive visual interpretation of cultivated land (agriculture class and bare land class) hence there was need of deriving statistics for better analysis.

	Forests in hectares	Build up area in hectares	Agriculture and bare land in hectares
1987	2382	271	32684
2000	4041	493	31270
2010	8313	658	26343

Table 1 Table showing distribution of various land covers in the study area.

The results from remote sensing image classification indicated increase in forest cover over the three periods analyzed. Growth in forest area may be an indication of more stringent measures adopted by the Kenya forest service (KFS). This could also indicate appreciation of the public to natural environment conservation and afforestation. However, the agricultural land has been

reducing. As shown, it reduced by 1414 hectares, and by 4927 hectares in 2000 and 2010 respectively.

Figure 4 A graph showing the comparison of changes in land cover per class.

4.2 NDVI analysis

The NDVI for the area of study showed varying minimum and maximum values. The maximum values for the year 1987, 2000 and 2010 were 0.730769, 0.637363 and 0.967213 respectively. The minimum values kept rising from -0.647059, -0.607143 to -0.384615 in 2010. This NDVI analysis of images spanning different months proved that the bare lands were actually cultivated lands in other seasons.

Figure 5 NDVI images for the year 1987, 2000 and 2010 respectively.

4.3 Population mapping and analysis

Upon population mapping, it can be noted that not only population has increased over the years but has also been more centered in Nyeri town. The total percentage around Nyeri town in the most recent census has increased to 16.11% compared to 15.09% and 13.14% in 1999 and in 1989 respectively.

Figure 6 A graph showing the population of the study area for the years 1989, 1999 and 2009.

The population growth however has decreased from 13% to 8% currently. This is an indication of increased urban sprawl and hence more pressure on land surrounding the urban area.

Figure 7 Population density maps showing the population distribution for the year 1989 and 1999 respectively.

The land use land cover results indicate increase in forest cover and urban area. The bare land was identified as cultivated but harvested land. The agricultural land was land with current active agriculture. So, for analysis, the two classes, i.e. the agricultural land and the bare land were analyzed as cultivated land.

The cultivated land was found to have declined over time possibly due to decline farmer compensation and exploitation by middle men. Coffee happens to be the major cash crop cultivated in the area of study. The growth of urban area has also encroached the agricultural land. The NDVI images also showed a clear progression in non-vegetative area in the southern area where Nyeri town is located. This meant that the vegetation cover in this area in particular was evidently reducing especially as changes in reflectance did not occur with seasons.

5 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The high population growth rate has resulted in pressure on land and planners need to consider population dynamics in planning for land use and policies affecting land use. Land use and land cover thematic maps were produced for the years 1987, 2000 and 2010. More composite data analysis of various factors affecting urbanization and population growth should be analyzed since population as a major causal factor but not the only one. Other relevant data such as on security, infrastructure development, health etc. should be considered in studies. High resolution imagery such as IKONOS could also be used to quantify accurately the areas of built up area and hence estimate the population without relying on census data which has a temporal resolution of 10 years.

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